
International Trade and Sustainable Agriculture

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ABSTRACT

A detailed examination of such a topic will be based on a fundamental problem, which will serve as a guiding principle in the presentation of the ideas underpinning the approach. In this case, it concerns the question of the links between international trade and sustainable agriculture. In other words, how do WTO trade policies combat...significant obstacles that distort trade in agricultural products, in order to establish a fairer trading system that will improve market access and increase the livelihoods of farmers worldwide?

Thus, the problem of method is central to all scientific work, as method illuminates hypotheses and determines conclusions. Our approach will be structured, with a few exceptions, around the use of analytical and exegetical methods, as well as comparative methods. This is understood as the analysis, interpretation, and explanation of legal rules, particularly those contained in the various legal texts of the GATT and the WTO.

As for the expected results, A truly effective international trading system cannot exclude the agricultural sector due to its specific characteristics. However, agriculture is less suited to a free trade and competition regime than the industrial and commercial world, which is by definition more mobile and adaptable. The 1947 General Agreement initially addressed agriculture, undoubtedly with some specific provisions, but gradually lost interest in it over the years. The WTO was to reverse this neglect and reintegrate agriculture, while granting it a transitional status. The Punta del Este Ministerial Declaration of September 1986, officially launching the "Uruguay Round," expressly mentioned agriculture as one of the subjects of future trade negotiations. Thus, for the first time in the history of multilateral trade negotiations sponsored by the GATT, the agricultural question was to be addressed; the general idea being to "liberalize" global trade in this sector. However, disagreements arose among industrialized countries regarding the liberalization of trade in agricultural products. The European Community, particularly France, the EFTA countries, Japan, and South Korea opposed a complete liberalization of trade. The United States and the Cairns Group, on the other hand, called for the elimination of export subsidies and the complete liberalization of trade in agricultural products within ten years. This liberalization was to be achieved by transforming all barriers to trade into tariffs. Developing countries also defended different positions depending on their circumstances. Studies had indicated that liberalizing agricultural trade and ending export subsidy policies would lead to an increase in global agricultural prices. Therefore, only net exporting developing countries would have benefited from trade liberalization. These countries had, moreover, joined the Cairns Group, and their interests aligned with those of developed countries like the United States and Australia. Net importing countries of agricultural products risked suffering from such liberalization. Consequently, they demanded the strengthening of food aid programs from developed countries towards them. However, the results of the negotiations point towards a liberalization of trade in agricultural products. The aim will therefore be to study the question of the gradual liberalization of the agricultural sector first by the GATT (Section I), then since the advent of the WTO with the Uruguay Round negotiations (Section II).

KEYWORDS : GATT, WTO, Liberalization, Agriculture, Sustainability

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SECTION I : THE GRADUAL LIBERALIZATION OF AGRICULTURE THROUGH THE GATT

Agricultural products are an important component of international merchandise trade. Their relative importance is undoubtedly decreasing, due to the ongoing industrial transformation affecting them and the human added value that now accounts for the

majority of the price of the most sophisticated and complex products, starting with those related to high technology. Nevertheless, in 1995, agricultural products represented 10% of world trade, or \$500 billion.

It is clear that a truly effective international trading system cannot exclude the agricultural sector because of its specific characteristics; however, it is less suited to being subjected to a free trade and competition regime than the industrial and commercial world, which is by definition more mobile and adaptable.

The 1947 General Agreement initially addressed agriculture, perhaps with some specific provisions, but gradually lost interest in it over the years. The WTO was to reverse this neglect and reintegrate agriculture into its framework, while granting it a transitional arrangement.¹

In principle, agricultural products were subject to the same general legal regime as industrial products. However, a certain degree of agricultural specificity existed, albeit limited. Over the years, agriculture de facto fell outside the jurisdiction of the GATT, while continuing to be, paradoxically, at the heart of numerous controversies and trade disputes.

This specific agricultural feature, found in the "GATT 1947," may well become the standard once the transitional regime established by the WTO has ended. It is characterized by rules adapted only in two areas: quantitative restrictions and subsidies, if we exclude agricultural products falling under the "non-GATT" category of raw materials. But the GATT would also incorporate regional economic integration.

Quantitative restrictions, due to their highly detrimental effect on international trade, are in principle unlawful under the code of good trade conduct established by the General Agreement, which enshrines the principle of exclusive customs protection. However, the General Agreement did allow, albeit with certain conditions, the legality of quantitative restrictions on both the export and import of agricultural products.²

A State is justified in resorting to quantitative restrictions on agricultural exports in a critical situation of "shortage".³In such a case, a state is justified in reserving domestic agricultural products for its national market and prohibiting their sale abroad: charity begins at home...

A State may also resort to "prohibitions or restrictions on imports or exports" if they are "necessary" to allow the application of standards intended for the "classification," "quality control," or "marketing" of agricultural products.⁴, all measures which may also be covered by the general exception in Article XX, paragraphs b) and d)⁵.

A State is also entitled, and this is by far the most frequent case, to resort to quantitative restrictions on imports of agricultural and fisheries products more generally.⁶Although this exception is broad, since it covers measures "necessary for the implementation of government measures," it does not, however, constitute a blank check for States, which must respect certain criteria in this area. These were explained in particular in two reports of the Special Group in 1988.⁷and especially 1989⁸It largely reflects the concerns and characteristics of American agricultural legislation between the two world wars.⁹

Generally speaking, such quotas are established within the framework of market organization policies through appropriate mechanisms to support agricultural product prices or farmers' incomes. This situation is relatively common. No state, except Great Britain in the second half of the 19th century, has ever been entirely free-trade in agriculture. For political and sociological reasons—namely, the desire to maintain a balance between urban and rural areas—and for strategic reasons—to preserve a strong and efficient agricultural sector—many states (if not all) have, to varying degrees, protected their domestic markets through quotas and/or subsidies.

From a pragmatic standpoint, the 1947 General Agreement had no choice but to acknowledge and formalize this reality. The central concern here is to ensure that these import quotas are indeed recognized as an essential and necessary component of national agricultural market organization mechanisms and are not separate from them. They must not constitute arbitrary and unjustified barriers to international trade intended to protect domestic agriculture.

Subsidies, both for production and especially for exports, are traditionally part of a protectionist policy, constituting its external component. Indeed, after shielding domestic producers from foreign competition through quantitative restrictions and encouraging them to produce, states must, in addition, facilitate the sale of these products on foreign markets. While the 1947 General Agreement was relatively strict with regard to industrial products, it offered considerable flexibility for agricultural products.¹⁰

¹CARREAU, D. JUILLARD, P. *International Economic Law*, pp. 158-166. Dalloz, 4th edition.

²Article XI, paragraph 2.

³Article XI, paragraph 2 a.

⁴Article XII, paragraph 2 b.

⁵For a discussion of this rarely invoked provision, see the 1988 Report of the Special (Panel) Group "Canada – Measures Affecting the Export of Unprepared Herring and Salmon", in *Guide to GATT Rules and Practices*, op.cit. p. 350-351).

⁶Article XII, paragraph 2 c.

⁷"Japan: Import restrictions on certain agricultural products."

⁸"Canada: Restrictions on the importation of ice cream and yogurt. See, *GATT Rules and Practices Guide*, op.cit. p. 352-354."

⁹See JACKSON, JH *World Trade and the law of GATT*, p. 319.

¹⁰Article XVI, paragraph 3.

Indeed, states can subsidize the agricultural exports of their national producers provided that the latter do not come to hold "more than a fair share" of the export market concerned by said product.

But how do we define what constitutes a more than equitable share of the market in question? This concept has consistently posed difficulties of interpretation and application throughout the history of the GATT. No concrete criteria have ever been established. Many agricultural disputes have focused on subsidies and their legality or illegality depending on their impact. There have been only rare instances where panels have been able to reach a precise conclusion. For example, in the 1958 case between Australia and France, the panel concluded that the French subsidy mechanism for certain cereals had enabled Australia to capture a "more than equitable share of the market" in Southeast Asia by crowding out traditional Australian exporters.¹¹ But, in all the agricultural disputes that pitted the United States against the EEC over the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), it was impossible to prove that Community subsidies via the technique of export refunds were illegal for having crossed this limit calculated in "fair" market share. It should be noted that the "Subsidies Code," adopted in 1979 at the Tokyo Round, shed little light on the matter, due to insufficient precision in the "criteria" it established regarding the product in question, in relation to the diversion of export flows in light of developments in world markets and "all special actors." In fact, agricultural disputes (particularly between the United States and the EEC or the United States and Japan), far from diminishing, only intensified and never reached a satisfactory settlement.

The General Agreement makes no mention of trade in agricultural products in its regulation of regional economic integration. It merely establishes the general rule that countries participating in both free trade areas and customs unions must eliminate all tariff and non-tariff restrictions covering "the substance of trade."¹² But what if agriculture as such is excluded from the scope of these integrations, as was the case, for example, with the European Free Trade Association (EFTA) established by the 1959 Stockholm Agreement? Over the years, the GATT considered the total or partial exclusion of agricultural products from the trade liberalization process to be legitimate and not to impede the application of this quantitative, but unquantified, trade requirement. This was yet another way of highlighting the specific nature of agriculture within the GATT.

Shortly after the General Agreement came into force, the United States adopted laws that went far beyond the specificities of agriculture and could not be justified by the exception regime of Article XI. This was particularly true of Article 22(f) of the Agricultural Adjustment Act, which prohibited and did not merely restrict the vast majority of agricultural imports. Faced with this situation, they requested and obtained, in 1955, a waiver under Article XXV(5) of the GATT, exempting them from the provisions of Article XI (and also Article II on national treatment). This waiver, granted without time limit, was still in effect when the GATT ceased to exist at the end of 1994, despite renewed criticism from the United States' partners, beginning with the EEC.

The granting of this broad exemption had far-reaching consequences. First, it effectively removed agriculture from the scope of the GATT. Second, it prevented the inclusion of agricultural products in multilateral trade negotiations organized under the auspices of the GATT, much to the dismay of the main exporting countries, both developed and developing. Finally, it fostered an acrimonious climate in international trade relations, where the "agricultural question" remained a constant source of conflict and controversy, particularly between the United States and the EEC. The former never missed an opportunity to criticize the latter's Common Agricultural Policy, while the Community had to do the same with regard to the exemption granted to the former in 1955, which isolated their agricultural market from international competition.

The "Uruguay Round" was fortunately intended to put an end to this conflict, at least temporarily.

SECTION II : THE PROGRESSIVE LIBERALIZATION OF AGRICULTURE SINCE THE ADVENT OF THE WTO

The Punta del Este Ministerial Declaration of September 1986, officially launching the "Uruguay Round," explicitly mentioned agriculture as one of the subjects of future trade negotiations. Thus, for the first time in the history of multilateral trade negotiations sponsored by the GATT, the agricultural question was to be addressed, the general idea being to "liberalize" global trade in this sector. Given the strong national compartmentalization of agricultural markets due to specific regulations supporting farmers' prices or incomes, any liberalization required a structural approach. Therefore, to promote market access, it was necessary to reduce barriers to imports, particularly in the non-tariff sector through sanitary and phytosanitary barriers, while to move towards a "fair" (and not free) market for agricultural products, it was necessary to address support measures for this sector—in other words, to tackle the highly sensitive issue of subsidies.

After many difficulties and crises that nearly derailed the Uruguay Round negotiations, an agreement on agriculture was finally concluded and subsequently annexed to the WTO under the heading of "multilateral agreements on trade in goods." Generally speaking, the reintegration of agriculture into the WTO system is manifested by the principled application of the "GATT 1994" and other multilateral agreements listed in Annex IA of the Marrakesh Agreement, subject to the specific and derogating provisions of this agreement on agriculture.¹³

¹¹See GATT Rules and Practices Guide, op.cit., pp. 490-491.

¹²Article XXIV, paragraph 8.

¹³Article 21 of the Agreement on Agriculture.

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The general legal character of "GATT 1994", in contrast to the specific and limited derogation that this agreement represents, was clearly highlighted by the Appellate Body in its report of September 9, 1997 in the case "European Communities – Regime applicable to the sale and distribution of bananas".

Given the highly technical nature of this agricultural agreement, only its main features will be briefly examined here. First, regarding the time factor, this agricultural agreement constitutes only the first phase in a liberalization process that must continue beyond this initial implementation period. Second, in order to make barriers to agricultural trade more transparent and understandable, these barriers will be transformed into tariffs, while commitments from member countries will be established to promote market access. Furthermore, member countries will be required to limit their domestic aid and export subsidies.

In general, the implementation of this agreement should take place over a period of six years starting in 1995.¹⁴ However, the situation is different with regard to the moderation commitment (sometimes referred to as the "peace clause") referred to in Article 13, which covers a period of nine years.

However, this agreement constitutes only a fundamental but merely the first step in the ongoing reform process. Given the scale of the task, the goal of liberalization can only be achieved in the long term, necessitating a continuous negotiation process. It is specified that new negotiations will begin one year before the end of each implementation period, namely in 1999 and 2003 respectively.¹⁵

Until then, the main barriers to agricultural imports took the form of non-tariff barriers. These are government measures of an administrative nature that share the common characteristic of not being based on price mechanisms. Here, as elsewhere, they are the most pernicious obstacles to world trade because it is impossible to overcome them through normal market mechanisms. Hence the revolutionary idea of transforming them into customs duties, according to complex calculation methods established by the agreement itself.¹⁶

The advantages are clear. These customs duties are transparent, easily identifiable, and easier to reduce during multilateral trade negotiations.¹⁷

In doing so, it is understood that trade in agricultural products falls under the general law of merchandise trade; this law, it should be remembered, is indeed based on the principle of exclusive customs protection. By quantifying restrictions on agricultural imports, these restrictions become transparent. This is already a significant factor in improving market access. Chile was thus censured for maintaining, in the form of a variable levy with a minimum import price, an import restriction measure that should have been converted into actual customs duties.¹⁸

Once the agricultural products concerned (they are listed in Annex 1) have been established, customs duties must be consolidated and reduced by 36% over a period of six years, with developing countries benefiting from a ten-year period and being required to make only a smaller reduction (24%).¹⁹

A specific safeguard clause, beyond certain triggering thresholds, has been included, the details of which will not be discussed due to its highly technical and complex nature.²⁰ We will limit ourselves here to mentioning three essential characteristics. First, the application of this clause excludes recourse to the general safeguard measures of GATT 1994.²¹ Furthermore, this clause will continue to apply throughout the ongoing and long-term process of reforming agricultural product trade.²² Finally, and most importantly, its implementation is always subject to minimum market access requirements in order to guarantee their gradual opening.²³

Thus, and the paradox is certain given the recent history of agricultural trade, thanks to this minimum market access clause, there is now a higher level of legal certainty for agricultural products than for industrial products.

Domestic support measures are a major feature of national (or EU) agricultural policies. WTO member countries have made commitments in this area that are remarkable for their complexity, and only the essentials will be mentioned here.

States have indeed committed to converting their domestic support measures for agricultural producers into a "global measure of total support" (or GMS), using highly technical calculation methods.²⁴ This overall support measure (OSM) will have to be gradually reduced by 20% during the six-year implementation period. Furthermore, and adding to the complexity of the mechanism, certain forms of public aid are not included in the calculation of this total OSM and are therefore not subject to any reduction

¹⁴Article 1) (f).

¹⁵Article 20.

¹⁶See article 4 (2) and Annex 5 (6) and (10) and the Appendix to Annex 5.

¹⁷See on this point the Appellate Body Report of 23 September 2002 – Chile – Safeguard measures applied to agriculture.

¹⁸See Chile – System of price bands and safeguard measures applied to certain agricultural products (Article 21.5 – Argentina, Appellate Body Report of 7 May 2007, WT/DS/2007/AB/RW).

¹⁹See Article 4(2) and Annex 5.

²⁰Article 5.

²¹Article 5.8.

²²Articles 5 (9) and 20.

²³Annex 5 (1).

²⁴Article 6 and especially Annex 3 which gives the parameters.

commitment.²⁵Overall, these are subsidies funded by public money and not intended to support producer prices. This excludes "public service programs," such as research subsidies or mechanisms to support farmers' incomes.

As an example of the great complexity of the subject matter and the difficulty of assessing the conformity of a domestic support measure with this aspect of the Agreement on Agriculture, reference is made to the Korea case – measures affecting imports of fresh, chilled and frozen beef.²⁶

These domestic support measures, provided they are "fully compliant" with the new provisions of the agreement on agriculture, are subject to a commitment to moderation by WTO member countries.²⁷This is what has sometimes been called the "peace clause" in agriculture, in relation to the heavy litigation of the GATT era. It expired on January 1, 2004.

If these are domestic support measures exempt from being included in the calculation of the MGS (what has sometimes been called the WTO's "green box"), then by not being subject to a reduction obligation, they will not be challenged under the "GATT 1994" and, in particular, will not be subject to countervailing duties under the subsidies regulations.²⁸If the measures in question are domestic support measures subject to the MGS regime (and other than *de minimis* measures), they can only be challenged as subsidies and be subject to countervailing duties under Article VI of the GATT 1994, that is, particularly if there has been damage or the threat of damage. This means that challenges remain possible, but in a limited way and governed by the principle of "moderation."²⁹

Export subsidies, which are more detectable but also harmful because they directly undermine fair trade, are subject to stricter special treatment.³⁰They are first more precisely defined using the techniques employed by public authorities, and member countries have subsequently committed to consolidating them and then reducing them by 36% over the standard six-year implementation period. In this area as well, developing countries (except the least developed among them) have a longer period of ten years and are required to achieve a smaller reduction (24%).³¹

However, they are subject to less "moderation" than the previous ones.³²While they may be subject to countervailing duties under the same conditions, they are not exempt from the "protection of concessions and advantages" mechanism of "GATT 1994".³³

This means that, at least in the long term, agricultural products will be subject to the same general regime as industrial products regarding export subsidies, which will thus be unified.

Despite some liberalization over the years, the agricultural sector remains heavily impacted by protectionism. According to a 2004 OECD study, agricultural support in wealthy countries amounted to \$305 billion, of which \$122 billion went to the European Union and \$88 billion to the United States. Similarly, tariff protection remains significant; *ad valorem* duties stand at 4% in the United States, 15% in the European Union, and 31% in Japan. The phenomenon of "tariff spikes" is also prevalent; for example, the United States taxes sugar imports at 15%, while the European Union levies a similar tariff of 63% on meat and Japan 290% on rice. However, alongside these visible non-tariff barriers, numerous other non-tariff barriers, though often "invisible," also pose serious obstacles to trade. This means that the liberalization of agricultural trade remains a major objective of the international community and rightly so, as it is one of the central objectives of the multilateral trade negotiations of the "Doha Round".

In other words, the objective of the Uruguay Round negotiating group on agricultural issues was ambitious. For the first time in the history of multilateral negotiations, the Punta del Este Ministerial Declaration contained no reference to the special status of agriculture within the GATT. The aim, therefore, was to restore agriculture to a normal status. Support and protection measures for agriculture were to be substantially reduced and, where possible, eliminated. The GATT was to exercise stricter controls over the remaining restrictive measures. Finally, access opportunities and modalities for agricultural products of particular interest to developing countries were to be significantly improved, especially with regard to tropical agricultural products.³⁴

The decision to finally incorporate the agricultural question into the Uruguay Round negotiations stemmed primarily from the desire of certain developed states to reform policies that had ultimately proven extremely costly and largely ineffective.

From the late 1960s onwards, voices were raised, particularly in Europe, calling for reforms to agricultural policies. As early as 1968, the Mansholt Report, presented by the European Commissioner for Agriculture, highlighted the dangers of the Common Agricultural Policy.³⁵

²⁵Article 6 (4) and (5) and especially Annex 2.

²⁶Report of the appeals body dated December 11, 2000.

²⁷Article 13.

²⁸Article 13 (a).

²⁹Article 13 (b).

³⁰Part V and Article 9 in particular.

³¹Article 9 (2) b iv) and 15.

³²Article 13 (c).

³³Article XXII.

³⁴ VINCENT, P. *The WTO and developing countries*, pp. 251-267.

³⁵For a full text, see *The Mansholt Plan – The Vedel Report*, Lafayette Group, 1969. For a commentary, see DEHOUSSE, F., VINCENT, P. (1998/5). "The Common Agricultural Policy or the Eternal Reform", pp. 49-50. *Studia Diplomatica*.

The reasons for these reform proposals were varied. As early as 1958, the Haberler Report had emphasized the problem of the place of developing countries on the international stage and their need for better access to the markets of industrialized countries. However, the main argument in European reform proposals was the exorbitant cost of agricultural policy for the budgets of developed countries.

Replacing guaranteed price systems with direct subsidies to farmers was proposed³⁶This had the advantage of reducing the price of agricultural products and the possibility of lowering trade barriers. Since farmers were no longer incentivized to increase their productivity, space could then be made for agricultural products imported from third countries. However, it was still necessary that a certain portion of these imports be reserved, in one way or another, for products originating from developing countries.

This economic logic was identical to that used against developing countries that imposed import restrictions. Trade liberalization was presented as a way to achieve a general increase in well-being. If certain sectors needed protection, it should be through direct subsidy payments to producers.

The talks within the agricultural negotiating group were unique in more ways than one. In particular, alongside the United States and the European Community, an independent negotiating force emerged: the Cairns Group. This coalition of fourteen major agricultural producers included both developed and developing countries.³⁷These groups defended common interests in agriculture. They wanted a liberalization of agricultural policies in the most protectionist industrialized countries, in order to increase their exports to those markets. Given its unique nature, the Cairns Group did not have any influence in other negotiating groups.

Disagreements existed among industrialized countries regarding the liberalization of trade in agricultural products. The European Community, particularly France, the EFTA countries, Japan, and South Korea opposed a complete liberalization of trade.³⁸The United States and the Cairns Group, on the other hand, demanded the elimination of export subsidies and the complete liberalization of trade in agricultural products within ten years.³⁹This liberalization was to be achieved by transforming all barriers to trade into customs tariffs.

Developing countries also defended different positions depending on their circumstances. Studies had indicated that liberalizing agricultural trade and ending export subsidy policies would lead to an increase in global agricultural commodity prices.⁴⁰Therefore, only net exporting developing countries would have benefited from trade liberalization. These countries had also joined the Cairns Group, and their interests aligned with those of developed countries like the United States and Australia.

Countries that were net importers of agricultural products risked suffering from such liberalization.⁴¹Consequently, they demanded the strengthening of food aid programs from developed countries towards them.⁴²

After numerous compromises and deadlocks⁴³The Uruguay Round negotiations resulted in the adoption of an agreement on agriculture containing several fundamental elements for trade in agricultural products. However, some of the most important provisions are not found in the text of the agreement itself. For example, it does not contain any quantified commitments to reduce tariffs. These provisions were included in Part B of the draft final agreement on agriculture presented by Arthur Dunkel (then Secretary-General of the GATT) in 1991.⁴⁴They did not acquire any legal status following the Uruguay Round negotiations. However, they were applied by WTO member countries in their tariff reductions, which were incorporated into their new schedules of concessions annexed to the agreement.⁴⁵

³⁶See. BREEN, J. "Agriculture", in STEWART, T. (1993). *The GATT Uruguay Round. A Negotiating History (1986-1992)*, t.1, pp. 160-162. Deventer, Kluwer.

³⁷It included Argentina, Australia, Brazil, Canada, Chile, Colombia, Fiji, Hungary, Indonesia, Malaysia, New Zealand, the Philippines, Thailand and Uruguay.

³⁸See the position of the European Community (doc. GATT MTN.GNG/NG5/W/145). For commentary, see ZEITZ, R. and VALDES, A. (1988). *Agriculture in the GATT: An Analysis of Alternative Approaches to Reform*, pp. 77-78. Washington, International Food Policy Research Institute.

³⁹See the United States proposal, doc. GATT MTN.GNG/NG5/W/118.

⁴⁰See. TYERS, R. ANDERSON, K. (1988). "Liberalizing OECD Agricultural Policies in the Uruguay Round: Effects on Trade and Welfare", pp. 197-216. *Journal of Agricultural Economics*; HOEKMAN, B. (1989/2) "Agriculture and the Uruguay Round", pp. 83-96. JWTL., GOLDIN, I. KNUDSEN, O. (1990). *Agricultural Trade Liberalization: Implications for Developing Countries*. Paris, OECD.

⁴¹See. HOEKMAN, B. (1989/2) "Agriculture and the Uruguay Round", pp. 83-96. JWTL., AWUKU, R. (1994/2) "How Do the Results of the Uruguay Round Affect the North-South Trade? »? pp. 75-93. JWTL.

⁴²See Jamaica's statement at the eighth meeting of the Negotiating Group on Agriculture (doc. GATT MTN.GNG/NG5/W/65).

⁴³For the history of agricultural negotiations during the Uruguay Round, see BREEN, J. "Agriculture," in STEWART, T. (1993). *The GATT Uruguay Round: A Negotiating History (1986–1992)*, vol. 1, pp. 172–226. Deventer: Kluwer. CLOOS, J., MARGUE, T.L. (1994). "The Agricultural Negotiations of the Uruguay Round," pp. 159–165. *Revue du Marché commun et de l'Union européenne*. JOSLING, T., TANGERMANN, S., WARLEY, T. (1996). *Agriculture in the GATT*, pp. 133–174. London: Macmillan.

⁴⁴Draft Final Agreement, pp. L19 to L34. For the final revised version of these provisions, see doc GATT MTN.GNG/MA/W/24.

⁴⁵See. JOSLING, T., TANGERMANN, S., WARLEY, T. (1996). *Agriculture in the GATT*, p. 182 and note 3. London, Macmillan.

Many of the new disciplines applicable to trade in agricultural products are therefore not included in the agreement itself. They are set out in the schedules of concessions of each Member State. These schedules are annexed to the Final Act of the Uruguay Round negotiations.⁴⁶The legal difference is significant. A member state can always renegotiate a bound agricultural tariff under Article XXVIII, paragraph 4 of the GATT. However, a specific numerical obligation contained within the text of the agreement itself should have been respected by each state. The only way to avoid compliance would have been to obtain a waiver from the WTO General Council.

The results of the negotiations point towards a liberalization of trade in agricultural products. All existing non-tariff barriers had to be converted into customs duties.⁴⁷An illustrative list of non-tariff barriers is included in Note 1 to Article 4 of the agreement. This list includes quantitative restrictions on imports, variable import levies, minimum import prices, discretionary import regimes, non-tariff measures applied through state trading enterprises, self-imposed export restrictions, and similar border measures other than actual customs duties, whether or not these measures are applied under waivers to the provisions of the 1947 GATT granted to certain countries. This last proposal specifically targeted the waiver granted to the United States in 1955. Consequently, this waiver could no longer be invoked as of January 1, 1995, the date of entry into force of the Agreement Establishing the WTO.

Article XI, paragraph 2(c) of the GATT was not amended by the Uruguay Round negotiators. Consequently, the paradoxical situation remains where quantitative restrictions on agricultural imports are permitted by the GATT but prohibited by the Agreement on Agriculture. This contradiction is resolved by the General Interpretive Note to Annex 1A of the Agreement Establishing the WTO. This note explicitly states that "in the event of a conflict between a provision of the GATT (...) and a provision of another agreement listed in Annex 1A (...), the provision of the other agreement shall prevail to the extent of the conflict." This general provision allowed the negotiators to avoid having to rewrite the GATT to reflect the new texts adopted.

To transform non-tariff barriers into customs duties, WTO member countries had to calculate the "tariff equivalents" of all the protection mechanisms they had previously used.⁴⁸The reference period chosen for tariff calculations was 1986-88, corresponding to the years when agricultural products reached their minimum cost. This allowed developed countries to calculate a significant difference between the world price of agricultural products and the prices charged in their markets. These differences, once tariffed, resulted in colossal figures. This mechanism led to a dizzying nominal increase in customs duties applied to agricultural imports. For the European Union, bound duties sometimes range from 150% to 300%. They amount, for example, to 274% for refined sugar, 254% for butter, and 174% for beef.⁴⁹However, this new situation has the advantage of predictability and consolidation.

Once established, customs duties were indeed subject to consolidation.⁵⁰For many agricultural products, the consolidation of their tariffs was a major first in the history of the GATT.

An exception to the immediate removal of non-tariff barriers to agricultural imports was included in the agreement. It allowed WTO member states, under certain conditions, to postpone until December 31, 2000, the phasing out of their import barriers to certain agricultural products.⁵¹This deadline could be extended if the country in question made further concessions to its trading partners. This clause became known as the "rice clause." It had, in fact, been inserted at the request of Japan and South Korea, concerned with protecting their domestic rice production.⁵²In exchange for this exception, Japan had to commit to opening an import quota higher than it would normally have had to agree to under the agreement.

For developing countries invoking Annex 5 of the agreement, the obligation to impose tariffs was deferred for ten years, until December 31, 2004. This period could also be extended if sufficient concessions were made to trading partners. South Korea and the Philippines invoked this clause for their rice imports, and Israel for its imports of mutton and goat meat, as well as certain dairy products. In exchange, these countries also had to commit to ensuring a minimum market access quota.⁵³

After being consolidated, tariffs were to be reduced by at least 36% over the period 1995-2001, in equal annual increments. This 36% reduction was intended as an average reduction, without weighting according to the relative importance of the sectors. States

⁴⁶Articles 3 and 4 of the agreement on agriculture.

⁴⁷Article 4, paragraph 2 of the agreement.

⁴⁸See MESSERLIN, P. (1995). *The new World Trade Organization*, p. 76. Paris, Dunod.

⁴⁹See OECD, *The Uruguay Round: Preliminary Assessment of the Consequences of the Agreement on Agriculture*, Paris, OECD, 1995. These figures often combine a fixed duty per quantity imported and an ad valorem duty. Estimates can therefore vary from one assessment to another, depending on the reference price chosen for each agricultural product. HATHAWAY, D., INGO, M., in "Agricultural Liberalization and the Uruguay Round," in MARTIN, W., WINTERS, A. (1996). *The Uruguay Round and Developing Countries*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, give tariffs of 297%, 288.5%, and 125.4%, respectively, for the three products mentioned. The order of magnitude, however, remains comparable.

⁵⁰Article 4 of the agreement.

⁵¹These agricultural products are designated by the symbol "TS-Annex 5" in section IB of part I of the list of each Member State that has invoked Annex 5 of the agreement.

⁵²See the proposal from the Republic of Korea, doc. GATT MTN.GNG/NG5/W/80. For a commentary, see JOSLING, T., TANGERMANN, S., WARLEY, T. (1996). *Agriculture in the GATT*, p. 180. London, Macmillan.

⁵³See the lists of concessions of these States.

could decide to reduce some sectors more significantly than others. However, each product had to see a reduction of at least 15%. A 60% reduction on two marginal, lightly protected products thus offset a 15% reduction on a sensitive product.

These provisions were not found in the text of the agreement but were in Part B of the 1991 pre-agreement. They were applied in the tariff concessions which were incorporated into the lists of concessions of the various partners annexed to the agreement.

Most developed countries have generally applied the lowest reductions (20% in the case of the European Community) to the most sensitive sectors, namely sugar, beef, and dairy products. These products remain subject to very high tariffs.⁵⁴The most significant reductions were granted on oilseeds and tropical products, which already had the lowest initial tariffs. Tariff protection therefore remained very high on sensitive products after the Uruguay Round negotiations. Consequently, the anticipated liberalization is often merely an illusion.

Member States also had to make concessions regarding access to their markets⁵⁵A "minimum access" equal to 3% of national consumption (5% on December 31, 2000) of each product must be guaranteed annually to foreign exporters. A reduced tariff, generally less than 32% of the normal rate, must be applied to this minimum access quota.⁵⁶These provisions were also not found in the text of the agreement but were applied in the lists of concessions of the WTO member states.

The agreement stipulates that developing countries should be given differentiated and more favorable treatment.⁵⁷, particularly the least developed countries⁵⁸.

This treatment takes two distinct forms. First, developing countries were given the option of implementing tariff reduction commitments over a period of up to ten years (instead of five). Their average tariff reduction was to reach 24% (instead of 36% for developed countries), with a minimum reduction of 10% (instead of 15%) in each sector. Least developed countries simply need to price their non-tariff barriers and bind the tariffs thus established. They are not obligated to make tariff reduction commitments.⁵⁹

Secondly, developing countries must receive concessions from developed countries regarding more favorable market access.

The agreement on agricultural products contains a special safeguard clause. A Member State may impose additional duties on imports of agricultural products when the volume of imports of that product exceeds existing market access possibilities or when the price at which those products are imported falls below the average reference price for the period 1986-1988.⁶⁰This duty varies depending on the difference between the import price and the reference price. It can therefore be considered a variable levy.⁶¹

No other type of measures is permitted under the agreement. Tariffs are definitively preferred to quantitative restrictions. This change, more than any other, seems to mark a return to the basic philosophy of the 1947 GATT, which already favored tariffs over quotas.

Only products for which customs duties have been consolidated will be eligible for safeguard measures. Each country had to specifically designate in its list the products for which it reserved the right to invoke such measures.⁶²This designation was made by affixing the symbol "SGS".⁶³next to the product listed. The additional duty imposed as a safeguard measure may not exceed one-third of the normally applicable customs duty. It may only remain in effect until the end of the year in which it was imposed.⁶⁴The operation of this safeguard clause must ensure transparency. Any State wishing to establish an additional right must inform the Committee on Agriculture as soon as possible.⁶⁵

The special safeguard clause does not include any measures to benefit developing countries. Consequently, the additional duties applied by developed countries under this clause will apply equally to exports from developing countries and those from developed countries.

In the context of an ultraliberal economic philosophy, the inclusion of such a safeguard clause is surprising. It maintains a genuine differentiation mechanism in a sector of crucial importance to developing countries, especially since no measures are planned to exempt them from this clause.

⁵⁴See. CAHILL, C. (October -November 1995). "Agriculture in the OECD area after Uruguay", no. 196, p. 33. OECD Observer.

⁵⁵Article 4, paragraph 1.

⁵⁶For a commentary, see SCHOTT, J., BUURMAN, J. (1994). *The Uruguay Round. An Assessment*, p. 51. Washington, Institute for International Economics.

⁵⁷Article 15.

⁵⁸Article 16.

⁵⁹Article 15, paragraph 2;

⁶⁰Article 5 paragraph 1. The complicated methods for setting the additional duty are set out in Article 5 paragraph 5 of the agreement on agriculture.

⁶¹See. HATHAWAY, D., INGCO, M., in "Agricultural Liberalization and the Uruguay Round", in MARTIN, W., WINTERS, A. (1996). *The Uruguay Round and Developing Countries*, p. 47. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.

⁶²Article 5, paragraph 1.

⁶³"Special backup".

⁶⁴Article 5, paragraph 4.

⁶⁵Article 5, paragraph 7.

Domestic support measures are criticized for harming international trade by keeping alive farms that would not be viable if they faced normal market rules.

The agreement on agriculture distinguishes three types of domestic support measures: the orange box, the green box and the blue box.

The orange box outlines the measures that distort competition. Members have agreed to reduction commitments. To assess the basis for these commitments, the overall support measure (OSM) for each product was calculated for each member. This corresponds to the difference between the domestic price and the world price multiplied by the production volume. Industrialized members had committed to reducing their OSM by 20% between 1995 and 2000. For developing countries, the reduction commitment was 13% between 1995 and 2004.

Two types of measures falling under the orange box benefit from an exception to the reduction obligation: *de minimis* subsidies that do not exceed 5% of the value of a product (10% for developing countries)⁶⁶ and measures to encourage agricultural and rural development in developing countries, as well as those aimed at encouraging the replacement of illicit narcotic crops⁶⁷.

The green box includes measures whose effects on trade are negligible or nonexistent. These are subsidies related to research, public health, and the creation of public food security reserves... They are not subject to reduction requirements.

The blue box includes direct aid to farmers linked to production reduction programs. This aid is not subject to reduction commitments as long as it meets one of the following three criteria: it is based on a fixed area and yields, or it covers 85% or less of the basic production level.⁶⁸ either they are carried out for a fixed number of head of livestock. These conditions, as if by chance, cover the direct compensatory payments put in place by the Community in 1992 and the American deficiency payments.

Indeed, the 1994 Agreement establishes a kind of "Richter scale" for subsidies based on their harmful and unfair effects on trade. Thus, some are simply prohibited, while others can be challenged; the latter being validated.⁶⁹

Regarding prohibited subsidies, a whole range of subsidies are prohibited as such. This falls under the so-called "red box" category. Export subsidies in general are prohibited and may not be granted or maintained.⁷⁰ In particular, subsidies linked to export performance or conditional on the use of domestic products to the detriment of imported products were singled out.⁷¹ Also included in this category are "tax exemptions," which are increasingly difficult to detect. For example, in the case "United States – Tax Treatment of Foreign Sales Companies," the appellate body had to determine that this measure did indeed constitute a subsidy creating an "advantage" through a "financial contribution" by waiving "normally due" public revenue. Furthermore, it constitutes a prohibited export subsidy, being "subordinated to export performance."⁷² Similarly, in the case of "Canada – Certain Measures Affecting the Automotive Industry", the non-collection of a customs duty was analyzed as a subsidy based on these same criteria, namely the waiver of a public revenue due and the dependence on export results.⁷³

If a WTO member country maintains or grants this type of subsidy, the Dispute Settlement Body (DSB) may be seized if consultations have not been successful within 30 days.⁷⁴ If a special group is formed, and a negative consensus would be needed to prevent it from being so.⁷⁵ He will have 90 days to submit his final report, with the WTO having 30 days to approve it, unless there is a negative consensus.⁷⁶ In the event of an appeal, the procedure may not exceed 60 days, and this is "under no circumstances," while the WTO will have 20 days to adopt this report, unless there is a negative consensus, which remains highly unlikely.⁷⁷ The particularly tight timeframe should be noted, as the procedure cannot exceed 230 days. While diligence is commendable in itself, it is reasonable to consider that the deadlines are excessively short, given the complexity of the economic and financial analyses to be carried out. Has speed been confused with haste? If the WTO's recommendation is not implemented, the complaining country will be authorized to take "appropriate countermeasures."⁷⁸

As for questionable subsidies, this refers to all "subsidies that may give rise to legal action".⁷⁹ that is to say, those which, due to their "adverse effects", are likely to be challenged by the affected Member States. This is the so-called "orange box" category.

⁶⁶Article 6, paragraph 4.

⁶⁷Article 6, paragraph 2.

⁶⁸With, therefore, an obligation to leave the land fallow.

⁶⁹See CARREAU, D., JUILIARD, P. *International Economic Law*, pp. 237-238. 4th edition, Dalloz.

⁷⁰Article 3 and see the "example list" in Annex I.

⁷¹For an example, see the DSB Report of August 2, 1999 in the case "Canada – Measures Relating to the Export of Civil Aircraft".

⁷²Report of January 14, 2002.

⁷³Report dated May 31, 2000.

⁷⁴Article 4, paragraphs 1 to 4.

⁷⁵Article 4, paragraph 4.

⁷⁶Article 4, paragraph 8.

⁷⁷Article 4, paragraph 2.

⁷⁸Article 4, paragraph 10.

⁷⁹Article 5 and in general Part III.

The adverse effects justifying the use of remedies consist of "damage caused to a domestic industry", a challenge to trade advantages consolidated under GATT 1994 or "serious harm" to the interests of other members which would originate from a "neutral" subsidy (i.e. non-specific in itself); the terms "subsidy", "serious harm" and "domestic industry" having the meanings given to them in the Agreement.

Similar remedies are provided for under the WTO Agreement⁸⁰The overall maximum time limit has been extended to 320 days, while remaining relatively short. If, within ten months of the adoption of the final report by the Dispute Settlement Body (DSB), the subsidy has not been withdrawn or its adverse effects have not been eliminated, the complaining country will be authorized to take "proportionate countermeasures."⁸¹

Regarding the approved subsidies, these are "subsidies not resulting in any action".⁸²that is to say, all those which are not "specific" or which, although they are, are specifically exempt⁸³This was a provisional measure concerning public funding for research and development, aid to disadvantaged regions, and environmental protection. This fell under the category known as the "green box". This exceptional regime was only intended to be temporary, initially limited to five years subject to extension. Without this extension, the regime has now lapsed.

From now on, the general rule is simple regarding subsidies: all those that cause "adverse effects to the interests" of WTO members are liable to be challenged.

The only remaining exception, and even that is also temporary, is that of "special and differential treatment" in favor of developing countries.⁸⁴

Negotiated by the United States and the European Community, the peace (or moderation) clause implied that support measures could not be challenged as long as the rules set out regarding market access, domestic support and export subsidies were respected.⁸⁵Intended for a period of nine years, it expired on January 1, 2004 without being renewed.

The agreement on agriculture contains a number of provisions on export subsidies for agricultural products as defined in Article 9, paragraph 1 of the agreement.

Other export subsidies are permitted provided they are not applied in a manner that results in, or threatens to result in, a circumvention of export subsidy commitments.⁸⁶

Export subsidies for developed countries had to be reduced, between January 1, 1995, and December 31, 2000, by 36% in terms of budgetary expenditures and by 21% in terms of export volumes compared to their levels during the 1986-1990 period. For developing countries, these percentages were 24% and 14%, respectively.⁸⁷At the time, there was no talk of abolishing them eventually. Further reductions were to be negotiated starting in 2000.⁸⁸

Each State's commitments regarding subsidies are listed in the schedule annexed to the Agreement. They cannot exceed these commitments. Two cases initiated by Brazil have been heard by the Dispute Settlement Body (DSB) concerning the issue of export subsidies.

In the case of the United States – subsidies concerning upland cotton⁸⁹The United States was condemned for offering its cotton producers export subsidies exceeding their commitments, on the grounds that payments under the Step 2 program, in favor of upland cotton exporters in the United States, were subsidies conditional on the use of domestic products in preference to imported products. The other case was much more complex. The European Community was condemned on October 15, 2004, for failing to respect its commitments regarding sugar exports.⁹⁰This case can be summarized as follows: the European Community distinguished three sugar production quotas: quota A, intended to satisfy community demand; quota B, which was to be exported, could benefit from import refunds; the remainder, outside the quota (sugar C), had to be exported without benefiting from refunds.

The Community had also committed to importing an annual quota of 1.6 million tonnes of sugar from the ACP countries and India at a guaranteed price. The quantities to be exported increased accordingly. In 1994, the Community committed to limiting its sugar export subsidies to 1.2735 million tonnes. A footnote excluded the 1.6 million tonnes imported at a guaranteed price from the subsidy reduction commitments. Both the panel report and the Appellate Body condemned the Community, on the grounds that the

⁸⁰Article 7.

⁸¹Article 7, paragraph 9 and italics added.

⁸²Part IV.

⁸³Article 8.

⁸⁴See Part VIII of the Agreement.

⁸⁵Article 13.

⁸⁶Article 10, paragraph 1

⁸⁷Article 9 paragraph 2 b) iv).

⁸⁸Article 20.

⁸⁹Case WT/DS267.

⁹⁰EC cases – sugar export subsidies WT/DS265 (Australia complaint), WT/DS266 (Brazil complaint) and WT/DS283 (Thailand complaint).

measures applied to quotas A and B resulted in an export subsidy for sugar C exceeding the Community commitment. They also refused to take the footnote into account.

To comply with the findings of the Dispute Settlement Body and the Appellate Body, the Community drastically reduced the guaranteed price for sugar imported from its partners⁹¹, with sometimes dramatic consequences for the economy of these states whose trade balance sometimes depends, for more than 20%, on sugar exports.

The consolidation and reduction of tariffs on agricultural imports are positive commitments to major exporting developing countries. However, they should not be misleading. The sectors most protected before the Uruguay Round negotiations saw the smallest reductions in applicable tariffs. These tariffs remain prohibitive and will continue to shield developed-country agriculture from external production for a long time. The reintegration of agriculture into the GATT framework is nonetheless a positive development. As future tariff reductions occur, developing countries should increasingly benefit from trade liberalization.

Market access granted by developed countries, particularly through minimum access clauses, should also benefit developing countries. The Japanese rice market, for example, will open up somewhat to exports from its neighbors, notably Thailand, which should also see an increase in its cassava exports to the European Community. The Voluntary Self-Restriction Agreement, concluded in 1982⁹²This agreement was effectively repealed by the agreement on agriculture. However, the consequences for developing countries that are net importers of agricultural products are less encouraging.

The provisions relating to the reduction of export subsidies for agricultural products risked leading to an increase in the price of agricultural products exported by developed countries. They are therefore favorable to developing countries that are major exporters of agricultural products. These countries will gradually be able to compete with exports from industrialized countries in third-country markets. The gradual reduction of subsidies will, however, slow the rise in prices. Developed countries have reserved for themselves a fairly long transition period to avoid excessively abrupt market losses.

However, at the end of the reduction process, net importing developing countries may have to pay more for the agricultural products they import. To address this issue, the Final Act includes a decision on measures concerning the potential negative effects of the reform program on least developed countries and net food-importing developing countries. Through this decision, developed countries commit to providing sufficient food assistance to developing countries that experience difficulties during the implementation of the reform program, and to considering their requests for technical and financial assistance.⁹³

Currently, the situation is at a standstill. Lacking an agreement among the main countries concerned (Australia, Brazil, the United States, India, Japan, and the European Union) on reducing domestic support measures for farmers, WTO Director-General Pascal Lamy announced on July 24, 2006, that all negotiations within the WTO were suspended indefinitely. Some observers at the time believed that the WTO would never recover from this setback, forgetting the difficulties encountered, for example, in 1990 during the Uruguay Round negotiations.

However, they resumed in February 2007. On February 8, 2008, a draft agreement on the terms for reducing domestic support measures was announced.⁹⁴Currently, however, no final agreement has been reached. On the contrary, the negotiations held in Geneva from July 21 to 29, 2008, ended in failure. A new draft agreement, part of the "July 2008 package," was distributed on August 11, 2008. It was subsequently supplemented in December 2008 by a revised draft of provisions concerning agriculture.

At the conclusion of the seventh WTO Ministerial Conference held in Geneva from 30 November to 2 December 2009, member states agreed that they would seek to reach a mutually beneficial solution for all in 2010.⁹⁵New negotiations took place from March 3 to 12, 2010.⁹⁶

Agriculture is undoubtedly the most contentious issue within the WTO. All members are affected. European and American farmers fear the eventual elimination of domestic support measures. This would lead to the disappearance of many of them, unable to compete with producers in the Southern Hemisphere. They therefore do not want a change in the situation, which they will, however, most likely be forced to accept.

The major producing countries and the United States are calling for the abolition of EU export subsidies. They also want (but without US support this time) the elimination of domestic support measures, including the green and blue boxes.

Small countries in the Global South are divided. Domestic support measures (e.g., aid to US cotton producers) harm their own farmers, preventing them from acquiring the global market share to which they could legitimately aspire. Conversely, export subsidies allow them to purchase agricultural products at low prices, which should prove beneficial to their populations. In reality,

⁹¹From 496.8 euros per tonne to 448.4 euros for raw sugar and from 631.9 euros to 541.4 euros per tonne for refined sugar.

⁹²OJEC 1982, L 219/52.

⁹³For a comment, see. SHAW, D., SINGER, H. (1996). "A Future Food Aid Regime: Implications of the Final Act of the Uruguay Round", pp. 447-460. Food Policy.

⁹⁴See document TN/AG/W/4/Rev.1.

⁹⁵See the summary of the Conference President, doc. WT/MIN(09)/18.

⁹⁶See http://www.wto.org/french/news_f/news10_f/agng_03mar10_f.htm.

these low-priced sales often backfire on their own farmers, who cannot compete and are sometimes forced to abandon their livelihoods.⁹⁷.

CONCLUSION

One thing is certain: without the WTO, the situation would be far worse. The agricultural policies of industrialized countries would be unchecked, and trade barriers would be extremely high. Farmers in the Global South would be unable to export their produce (even to other developing countries), while those in the Global North could continue to produce at uncompetitive prices, shielded by insurmountable barriers. The production of uncompetitive goods under protectionist measures and the lack of open markets are precisely the criticisms that developed countries constantly level at developing countries. Thus, for years, developed countries have been speaking with a forked tongue in the agricultural sector, in the name of ensuring domestic food supply.

Developed countries, particularly the European Union, are nonetheless calling for open markets for goods and services from developing countries. The EU is also demanding the integration of Singapore's policies into the WTO's rules. Its room for maneuver is therefore very limited. The only concessions it can still make are precisely in the agricultural sector. However, the influence of European agricultural lobbies, which are reluctant to accept significant reductions in support measures, is well known. Now that the largest developing countries are speaking with one voice, it is highly likely that it will be difficult to extract concessions from them without paying a heavy price.

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⁹⁷See, for example, the survey carried out by SOS Faim on the disappearance of the poultry sector in Cameroon following subsidized imports of frozen community chickens into that country, in *Dynamiques paysannes*, May 2004 (available at <http://www.sosfaim.be/pdf/fr/dp/DP4.pdf>).